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Wind fields from atmospheric turbulence measurements

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Abstract. We present recent advances in the modeling of wind fields and their reconstruction from real-world atmospheric turbulence measurements. The proposed wind field model provides a statistically coherent framework for modeling the empirically observed occurrence of extreme atmospheric events. Furthermore, we demonstrate that the model is general enough to enmesh real-world measurement points, e.g., from meteorological masts or LIDAR, and thus provides a rather convenient method for the reconstruction of highly resolved, three-dimensional wind fields. Our methodology is based on the so-called superstatistics of Gaussian-distributed (or Mann-type) velocity fields with fluctuating covariances and exactly reproduces higher-order statistics due to extreme small-scale wind fluctuations. Therefore, it could lead to more realistic inflow conditions and might potentially enhance the current design standard of wind turbines. We further discuss potential applications of the wind field model in the context of LIDAR measurements as well as for wake situations.

1. Introduction

The ever-increasing size of wind turbines, which might eventually exceed the height of the atmospheric surface layer, leads to new challenges for the design process and operation of modern wind turbines [1, 2]. Therefore, wind energy applications are in strong need of novel methods such as the use of reduced-order surrogate models or new ground-based systems, e.g., advanced LIDAR or SODAR, as well as aerial measurement campaigns with drones or airplanes. Contrary to the relatively steady and controllable power output of nuclear or combustion plants, the operating conditions and power output of wind farms are heavily influenced by extreme wind fluctuations [2, 3, 4]. Latter may only be detectable on time scales that are smaller than one second but can nevertheless affect the power output of the entire wind plant, sometimes even leading to a power increase of more than eighty percent.

Empirically, the occurrence of such extreme wind gusts is closely related to the phenomenon of small-scale intermittency and manifests itself by strong deviations from Gaussian statistics of wind fluctuations. Current design standards [5], however, do not capture the non-Gaussianity, non-stationarity, and non-homogeneity of turbulent inflow conditions. This inevitably leads to maintenance issues or material fatigue due to unpredictable loads, for example on the rotor or the blades. The cost of such “unexpected failures” and subsequent maintenance over the typical 20-year lifespan of a wind turbine is hard to estimate but is sometimes assumed to lie in between 65 and 95 percent of the initial cost of the turbine [6].

Inflow turbulence models such as the Mann, Kaimal, or Veers model [7, 8] are based on Gaussian random fields that can be efficiently sampled by prescribing certain spectral tensorial forms. Therefore, the latter models are frequently used on an industrial level in order to achieve a certain standard of product reliability [1]. Nonetheless, non-Gaussian statistics of such stochastic wind field models have only been incorporated in a temporal sense [9, 10], i.e., without accounting for spatial coherence in the rotor plane. Recently, a “superstatistical” wind field model was proposed where intermittency of a fully three-dimensional wind field is exactly controllable and where real-world measurement data can be integrated in the sense of a “constrained” wind field [11, 12].

In this contribution, we discuss current and potential future applications of this wind field model at the example of meteorological mast array measurements [13, 14], LIDAR measurements, and the modeling of turbine wakes. The paper is organized as follows, Section 2 and 3 give an account of the modeling framework, Section 4 describes potential future applications, whereas concluding remarks are given in Section 5.

2. Superstatistical wind field model

This section reviews the superstatistical wind field model proposed in refs. [13, 15]. To this end, we first present the statistical description of current wind field models covered by standards of the International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC) [5]. Characteristics of the atmospheric turbulence in such Gaussian wind field models such as the Mann, Veers, or Kaimal model enter through the covariance tensor of the random field $\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x})$, i.e.,

$$\sigma_{i\alpha,j\beta} = \langle u_\alpha(\mathbf{x}_i)u_\beta(\mathbf{x}_j) \rangle , \quad (1)$$

where brackets denote a suitable averaging procedure (e.g., ensemble averaging or temporal averaging). In the homogeneous and isotropic wind field models of the IEC standard, the Fourier transform of the covariance tensor (1) is entirely defined by the energy spectrum $E(k)$ according to

$$\langle \hat{u}_\alpha(\mathbf{k})\hat{u}_\beta(\mathbf{k}') \rangle = \frac{1}{(2\pi)^6} \int d\mathbf{x}_i \int d\mathbf{x}_j e^{-i\mathbf{k}\cdot\mathbf{x}_i - i\mathbf{k}'\cdot\mathbf{x}_j} \langle u_\alpha(\mathbf{x}_i)u_\beta(\mathbf{x}_j) \rangle = \delta(\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{k}') \left(\delta_{\alpha\beta} - \frac{k_\alpha k_\beta}{k^2} \right) \frac{E(k)}{4\pi k^2}, \quad (2)$$

where $\delta(\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{k}')$ denotes the Dirac delta distribution and $\delta_{\alpha\beta}$ the Kronecker delta. For intermediate wavenumbers the energy spectrum possesses the universal form $E(k) \sim k^{-5/3}$, whereas additional features of atmospheric turbulence such as shear lead to slightly different tensorial forms [5]. Fixing the mean $\mathbf{U} = \langle \mathbf{u} \rangle$ and the covariances (1) in a Gaussian model fully determines the statistics of the wind field characterized by the so-called joint multipoint probability density function

$$f_n(\mathbf{u}_1, \mathbf{x}_1; \dots; \mathbf{u}_n, \mathbf{x}_n) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{(2\pi)^{3n} \det \sigma}} e^{-\frac{1}{2}(u_{i,\alpha} - U_\alpha)\sigma_{i\alpha;j\beta}^{-1}(u_{j,\beta} - U_\beta)}. \quad (3)$$

Such Gaussian random fields can be sampled efficiently in Fourier space. Nonetheless, as already highlighted in Section 1, they do not account for a crucial feature of atmospheric turbulence, i.e., the occurrence of extreme wind fluctuations. Figure 1(a) shows the probability distribution $h(v, r)$ of wind field fluctuations $v(r) = u(x+r) - u(x)$ at a fixed scale $r = 0.0044L$ (L denotes the so-called integral length scale or correlation length of the wind) determined from the GROWIAN measurement data consisting of 16 propeller anemometers distributed on two meteorological masts [16, 17]. Current wind field models in the IEC standard predict a Gaussian distribution for $h(v, r)$, which is represented by the turquoise curve in Figure 1(a) and has the same standard deviation as the measurement data (orange). Hence, IEC standard models underestimate the

Figure 1. (a) Probability distribution of wind field fluctuations $h(v, r)$. Temporal increments have been converted based on Taylor's hypothesis (see ref. [13] for further details).

occurrence of extreme wind fluctuations (e.g., those belonging to $|v| > 4$ m/s, i.e., tails of the probability distributions).

The main idea of the superstatistical approach [13, 15, 18] consists in considering a superposition of the multivariate Gaussian distributions (3) according to

$$f_n(\mathbf{u}_1, \mathbf{x}_1; \dots; \mathbf{u}_n, \mathbf{x}_n) = \int_0^\infty d\xi g(\xi) \frac{1}{\sqrt{(2\pi)^{3n} \det \sigma_\xi}} e^{-\frac{1}{2}(u_{i,\alpha} - U_\alpha) \sigma_{\xi, i\alpha; j\beta}^{-1} (u_{j,\beta} - U_\beta)}. \quad (4)$$

Here, the covariances $\sigma_{i\alpha; j\beta}$ in Eq. (3) have been re-parameterized as $\sigma_{\xi, i\alpha; j\beta}$ by introducing fluctuations between two spatial points

$$r_{ij} = |\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_j| \rightarrow \rho_\xi(r_{ij}) = \xi \sqrt{A + \mu \ln + \frac{x^\rceil}{r_{ij} + x^\rceil}} \left(\frac{r_{ij} + x^\rceil}{x^\rceil} \right)^{\frac{\mu}{2}} r_{ij}, \quad (5)$$

where x^\rceil is a small-scale cut-off whereas x^\rceil and A represent large-scale flow characteristics. Deviations from Gaussianity are characterized by the intermittency coefficient μ in combination with fluctuations ξ that follow a lognormal distribution $g(\xi)$, which mimics the influence of fluctuations of the local energy dissipation rate in the turbulent flow [19]. The superstatistics (4) is illustrated by the probability distributions of wind field fluctuations in Figure 1(b). Here, the orange curve represents a superposition of Gaussian distributions with fluctuating variances (indicated by the three dashed black curves). As in Figure 1(a), the latter parametrization can precisely control the occurrence of small-scale extremes $u(x+r) - u(x)$ by the so-called intermittency coefficient μ . In other words, the superstatistical approach can formally extend *any* standard model of the IEC norm (represented by the covariances $\sigma_{i\alpha; j\beta}$) in order to account for heavy-tail behavior due to the occurrence of small-scale extremes. The additional model parameter μ has to be determined from real-world measurements (e.g., $\mu = 0.243$ for the GROWIAN data set [13]) and could be strongly site-dependent. Furthermore, as the superstatistics forms a so-called *Gaussian scale mixture*, wind fields can be sampled in a relatively efficient way that consists of generating multiple Gaussian random fields (e.g., of Mann-type but with re-parameterized covariances) $\mathbf{u}(\xi, \mathbf{x})$ with the same noise realization and subsequent scale mixing (see ref. [13] for further details on the sampling algorithm). The following section describes how the proposed framework can reconstruct wind fields from sparse real-world measurements.

Figure 2. Reconstructed wind field from the GROWIAN measurement array that consisted of 16 propeller anemometers mounted on two meteorological masts (grey).

3. Reconstruction of turbulent wind fields from atmospheric turbulence measurements

The wind field model proposed in the previous section can be apprehended as an extension of the standard IEC models by an additional parameter, the so-called intermittency coefficient μ , which characterizes heavy-tailed behavior of the PDF of wind field fluctuations at small scales as demonstrated in Figure 1. The advantage of sampling the wind fields from such a Gaussian scale mixture is that methods that are valid for Gaussian statistics (3), such as the conditioning of the stochastic process on measurement points [11, 12], can also be applied to the superstatistical wind field. As it has been shown for the GROWIAN data set consisting of time series of 16 propeller anemometers arranged in a meteorological mast array [13], the framework can constrain the stochastic wind field $\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x})$ on measurement \mathbf{U}_i measured at points (\mathbf{x}_i) by a so-called bridge construction

$$\mathbf{u}^B(\xi, \mathbf{x}) = \mathbf{u}(\xi, \mathbf{x}) - [u_\alpha(\xi, \mathbf{x}_i) - U_{\alpha,i}] \sigma_{\xi,i\alpha;j\beta}^{-1} \langle u_\beta(\xi, \mathbf{x}_j) \mathbf{u}(\xi, \mathbf{x}) \rangle . \quad (6)$$

A reconstructed wind field is shown in Figure 2. Thereby the bridge construction (6) is an exact interpolation of the pointwise GROWIAN measurements as it fulfills $\mathbf{u}^B(\xi, \mathbf{x}_i) = \mathbf{U}_i$. Nonetheless, we emphasize that the proposed framework is general enough to “constrain” the wind field on any observable, which will be discussed in the following section.

4. Potential future applications and further validation of the superstatistical model

In this section, we describe future applications and potential validations of the wind field model from LIDAR measurements of turbulent inflow and in wake situations.

4.1. Reconstruction of spatiotemporal wind fields from line-of-sight LIDAR measurements

The superstatistical model has only been validated based on the GROWIAN data. Hence, it would be desirable to perform further validations on the basis of more finely resolved wind fields, e.g., from LIDAR or SpinnerLIDAR [20, 21, 22]. The framework (4) can be extended to account for the spatiotemporality of wind field measurements $\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ by introducing the covariances

$$\sigma_{i\alpha;j\beta} = \langle u_\alpha(\mathbf{x}_i, t_i) u_\beta(\mathbf{x}_j, t_j) \rangle , \quad (7)$$

measured at two distinct points in space *and* time. Under the assumption of Taylor's hypothesis, the latter covariances can be simplified according to [19]

$$\sigma_{i\alpha,j\beta} = \langle u_\alpha(\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{U}(t_i - t_j), t_i) u_\beta(\mathbf{x}_j, t_i) \rangle , \quad (8)$$

where \mathbf{U} denotes a mean velocity field. Hence, assuming that the mean flow merely advects the turbulence allows for modeling a spatiotemporal field by the joint statistics (4). Furthermore, the bridge construction (6) can be reformulated to only constrain the wind field on the instantaneous radial component of the wind field available from the line-of-sight measurements from LIDAR. Therefore, a systematic reconstruction of the wind field, e.g., from SpinnerLIDAR trajectories as outlined in [23], should offer further possibilities for validating the superstatistical model.

4.2. Modeling of turbine wakes

As demonstrated in the previous sections, the wind field model proposed in Section 2 can be considered a somewhat realistic model of an atmospheric flow. Nonetheless, it relies on certain assumptions, such as the homogeneity or isotropy of the turbulent flow. Vertical velocity profiles due to shear are only taken into account by adding an external shear field and - as of now - do not enter the covariance tensors in the superstatistics (4), as it is for instance the case in the Mann model [8], which uses rapid distortion theory. Hence, we implicitly assume that the small-scale statistics of atmospheric turbulent wind fields are somehow unaffected by large-scale anisotropies, which might be valid for turbulent inflow. Nevertheless, wind energy converters are usually clustered in wind farms implying that downstream turbines operate in the wake of the upstream turbines. Therefore, wind velocities in the wake are typically lower than inflow, whereas turbulence intensities are more pronounced [24]. Accurately predicting extreme wind fluctuations thus plays a crucial role in subsequent turbine load calculations or load-surrogate models [25]. Due to the Gaussian scale mixture described in Section 2, it could be possible to model different regions by an adaptive superposition of Gaussian statistics and thus mixing flows composed of sub-flows with different turbulent levels. Ultimately, results obtained from such refined dynamic wake wind field models (taking into account the effects of wake meandering or tip-vortex instabilities [26]) could lead to potential improvements of current engineering models [27].

5. Conclusions

We have presented an extension of current Gaussian wind field models in the IEC norm by including an additional parameter, the so-called intermittency coefficient μ , which characterizes the statistical significance of the occurrence of extreme wind fluctuations. It will be a task for future research to further assess the implications of this additional parameter, which characterizes the statistical significance of extreme wind gusts. Next to more elaborate aerolastic simulations, a first assessment of the different behavior of IEC models and extended (i.e., non-Gaussian) models could be the wind speed averaged over the rotor plane. Consequently, the wind field model could be relevant for a broad range of applications ranging from the enhancement of incomplete measurements to the improvement of load calculations and ultimately improved design standards.

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